

LESSON PLAN IN MATHEMATICS 9

Applications of Radicals

Content Standard: The learner demonstrates understanding of key concepts of variation and radicals.

Learning Competency: The learner solves problems involving radicals (M9AL-IIj-1).

Performance Standard: The learner is able to formulate and solve accurately problems involving radicals.

Specific Objectives: The learner is able to:

- illustrate the information from the problem.
- generate the steps in solving problems involving radicals.
- solve problems involving radicals.

References: Grade 9 Mathematics Teacher's Guide pp 191-196
Grade 9 Learner's Material pp 280-292
Math Connections in the Digital Age 9 pp158-169
Making Connections in Mathematics II pp 174-180
Teacher-Made SLM

Other Materials: Worksheet, Powerpoint Presentation

Procedures:

1. Reviewing Previous Lesson or Presenting New Lesson

- WARM UP Activity!** Determine whether the given values satisfy the given radical equation. If the value satisfies the radical equation, write S. If not, write NS.

- | | | |
|------------------------------|--------------|-------------|
| 1. $\sqrt{x} = 4$ | a. $x = -16$ | b. $x = 16$ |
| 2. $x - 4 = \sqrt{2x}$ | a. $x = 2$ | b. $x = 8$ |
| 3. $2 + \sqrt{x + 10} = x$ | a. $x = 6$ | b. $x = -1$ |
| 4. $\sqrt{19 - 3x} - 1 = 3x$ | a. $x = 1$ | b. $x = -2$ |
| 5. $3\sqrt{x - 2} + 2 = x$ | a. $x = 2$ | b. $x = 11$ |

2. Establishing a Purpose for the Lesson

- The learner solves problems involving radicals.

3. Presenting Examples/Instances of the Lesson

- I Need to Solve!**

The equation $G = 89 + \sqrt{P - 5}$, where G is the grade and P is the number of completed problems, models the grade of Terry in her Mathematics exam. If Terry is aiming for 91%, how many problems does she need to practice?

Guide questions:

- What does the equation $G = 89 + \sqrt{P - 5}$ represent in the problem?

- b. How is the grade (G) related to the number of completed problems (P) in Terry's Mathematics exam?
- c. What is Terry's target grade in the exam?
- d. How will you solve the problem?

4. Discussing New Concepts and Practicing New Skills#1

- Process the answers of the students.
- What are the steps in solving problems involving radicals?
- Present this problem and let the students answer. Afterwards, ask one students to show and explain the solution.

Dan the Swimmer: When Dan swims, the number of meters he covers is related to the number of fruits and vegetables he eats five weeks before his game. The equation is $d = 12 + \sqrt{5f}$ where d is the distance in meters Dan swam and f is the number of fruits and vegetables he ate. If Dan covered 500m, how many fruits and vegetables did he eat?

5. Developing Mastery (Leads To Formative Assessment 3)

The Happy Equation: Pedro's happiness is directly proportional to the number of minutes he plays basketball. This relationship can be modeled by the equation $h = 25 + \sqrt{50s}$ where h is happiness units and s is the number of minutes he played basketball. If Pedro has 70 happiness units, how many minutes of basketball did he play?

6. Finding Practical Application of Concepts and Skills in Daily Living

- Decision making is part of human's life. Sometimes, we commit mistake but what is important is that we learned from it. Learning from mistakes can help you to be a better person. Have you committed mistake/s? What did you learn from it?

7. Making Generalization and Abstractions about the lesson

- What are the steps in solving problems involving radicals?
- What are the mathematical concepts need to solve problems involving radicals?

8. Evaluating Learning

- **Answer each problem.**
 1. The formula for the slant height of a cone is $c = \sqrt{h^2 + r^2}$, where h is the height of the cone and r is the radius of its base. Find the height of the cone if the slant height is 4cm and the radius is 2cm.
 2. Gary's happiness is directly proportional to the number of hours he reads story books. Let us say this relationship can be modeled with the equation $h = 2 + \sqrt{3s}$ where h is happiness units and s is the number of story books she had read. If Gary has 8 happiness units, how many story books did he read?